

Saving the world under agricultural law or overtaxing it? – On the methodology of integrating non-agricultural claims into European agricultural law¹

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Abstract

Au fil de son évolution, la politique agricole commune a été confrontée, à partir de l'organisation des marchés agricoles, à de nombreuses matières différentes et non agricoles. Il a fallu faire face aux exigences de la protection de l'environnement, de la politique structurelle et sociale, du bien-être animal, de la politique énergétique ou de la protection du climat. Aujourd'hui, on observe trois méthodes différentes, à savoir la séparation, la combinaison et l'intégration, qui permettent d'organiser juridiquement la relation entre le droit agricole et les matières juridiques non agricoles. Une analyse finale montre les limites de ce qui est réalisable.

Die Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik wurde im Lauf der Entwicklung von der Ordnung der Agrarmärkte aus mit vielen unterschiedlichen und außerlandwirtschaftlichen Materien konfrontiert. So galt es sich den Anforderungen von Umweltschutz, Struktur- und Sozialpolitik, Tierwohl, Energiepolitik oder Klimaschutz zu stellen. Heute lassen sich mit Trennung, Verknüpfung und Integration drei unterschiedliche Methoden beobachten, mit denen die Beziehung zwischen Agrarrecht und agrarfremder Rechtsmaterie juristisch gestaltet wird. Eine abschließende Analyse zeigt die Grenzen des Machbaren auf.

1. Introduction

As is well known, European agricultural law is based on Articles 38 to 44 TFEU and thus has an open and relatively lean mandate for action. The five classical objectives mentioned in Article 39 TFEU – increasing productivity, ensuring a fair standard of living for the agricultural community, stabilising markets, assuring supplies, supplying consumers at reasonable prices – are to be pursued by means of one of the three instruments provided by Article 40 (1) TFEU. These are common competition rules, compulsory coordination of the various national market organisations and a European market organisation. Option 3 was chosen early on, as only a European market organisation at the beginning of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was considered to be sufficiently suitable to achieve the objectives, and in particular to remedy the shortages after the Second World War.

On this basis, European agricultural law was subsequently developed, a body of law which is probably unparalleled within European law in terms of scope and level of detail². In the process, the thematic basis was continuously expanded, whereby on the one hand the agricultural policy agenda itself was continually developed, and on the other hand other policies were integrated to a greater or lesser extent. This article first attempts to outline the most important of these expansions (Chapter 2) and

¹ Revised and translated version of R. Norer, *Agrarrechtliche Weltenrettung oder Überforderung? Von der Methodik der Integration außerlandwirtschaftlicher Ansprüche ins europäische Agrarrecht*, Festschrift for Roman Budzinowski, *Przeegląd Prawa Rolnego* 2/2021, pp. 349 ff.

² J. Schwarze, *Europäisches Verwaltungsrecht*, 2nd edition, Baden-Baden 2005, p. 380.

then to systematise (Chapter 3) and analyse (Chapter 4) the instruments used to address these new issues.

2. Extensions

Compared to the initial situation at the time of the Stresa Conference of July 1958, which was in accordance with the mandate of ex-Art. 43 (1) of the EEC Treaty³, the current thematic breadth may be surprising. Nevertheless, it was not without reason that the primary legislation was conceived as a framework regulation, in order to allow sufficient leeway for the concrete political design depending on the branches and forms of business, geographical regions and countries, topics and times.⁴ This primary law control deficit has hardly had a negative effect and has only made possible the transformations described here.

2.1 Market regulation

The actual legal start of the CAP dates back to 1962 with the first regulations for the gradual establishment of the common market organisations (CMOs)⁵, which could be concluded for most products by 1970.⁶ These regulations presented themselves exclusively as being of a genuine agrarian legal character, comprising in particular price and trade regulations, intervention measures, import licences and refunds, plus the basic rules for financing the CAP. No more and no less.

The further development of this core component of European agricultural law was then marked by the undesirable developments of the 1980s and early 1990s, which manifested themselves in surplus production (the proverbial milk lakes and butter mountains) and the associated extreme financial burdens. It was not until the 1992 CAP reform (MacSharry reform), which is still groundbreaking today⁷, with its move away from price guarantees towards direct area and yield-oriented income subsidies, that the economic instruments were sustainably transformed.

After the continuation within the framework of “Agenda 2000”⁸, the 2003 reform (Fischler reform)⁹ was able to take a further radical step with the introduction of the production-independent single farm payment, whereby in retrospect this reform stage presents itself as Janus-faced: on the one hand

³ Cf. R. Norer, *Die Zukunft der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik: Europarechtlicher Trendsetter oder Expertenhochburg?*, in: R. Norer, G. Holzer (eds.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2020*, Vienna 2020, p. 217; O. Gottsmann, Art. 43 EWGV para. 2, in: H. von der Groeben, H. von Boeckh, J. Thiesing, C.D. Ehlermann (eds.), *Kommentar zum EWG-Vertrag*, 3rd edition, Baden-Baden 1983.

⁴ See R. Norer, Art. 38 TFEU para. 4, in: M. Pechstein, C. Nowak, U. Häde (eds.), *Frankfurter Kommentar EUV, GRC und AEUV*, Vol. II, Tübingen 2017, with further references.

⁵ In addition, Regulation (EEC) No. 25/1962 on the financing of the common agricultural policy, OJ 1962, No. 30/991; Regulation (EEC) No. 26/1962 applying certain rules of competition to production of and trade in agricultural products, OJ 1962, No. 30/993.

⁶ E.g. Regulation No 120/67/EEC on the common organisation of the market in cereals, OJ 1967, L 117/2269; Regulation No 121/67/EEC on the common organisation of the market in pigmeat, OJ 1967, L 117/2283; Regulation (EEC) No 805/68 on the common organisation of the market in beef and veal, OJ 1968, L 121/67. Also Regulation (EEC) No 729/70 on the financing of the common agricultural policy, OJ 1970, L 94/13.

⁷ Regulations (EEC) No. 1765/92 and 1766/92, OJ 1992, L 181/12 ff; Regulation (EEC) No. 2066/92-2080/92, OJ 1992, L 215/49 ff.

⁸ Regulation (EC) No 1251/1999-1259/1999, OJ 1999 L 160/1 et seq.; Regulation (EC) No 1493/1999, OJ 1999 L 179/1.

⁹ Regulation (EC) No 1782/2003-1788/2003, OJ 2003 L 270/1 et seq.; Implementing Regulation (EC) No 795/2004 and 796/2004, OJ 2004 L 141/1 et seq.

as a further development of the reform steps introduced in 1992, on the other hand as a system break due to the fundamental decoupling of direct payments¹⁰.

The 2013 reform¹¹ finally abandoned the allocation of payment entitlements based on historical reference values and replaced it with the basic payment scheme. Subsequently, the expiry of milk quotas in 2015 and sugar quotas in 2017 led to the abandonment of decades of central agricultural regulatory systems, followed by the appearance of new safeguard clauses and the extension of the recognition of producer organisations and interbranch organisations to all sectors on the agricultural legal stage.

2.2 Environmental protection

Despite various earlier developments¹², aspects of a separate agri-environmental policy emerged clearly for the first time in the context of the 1992 CAP reform. The agri-environmental programmes to be offered by the Member States under Regulation (EEC) No. 2078/92¹³ served to ensure agricultural production methods compatible with the requirements of the protection of the environment and the maintenance of the countryside. With the 1999 reform (“Agenda 2000”) this legal framework was then incorporated as a flanking measure into the newly created 2nd pillar of the CAP¹⁴, where it still exists today¹⁵ – alongside numerous other measures, some of which are also ecologically oriented. As a rule, five- to seven-year commitments are made which aim to maintain and promote necessary changes in agricultural practices that have a positive impact on the environment.

With Agenda 2000, however, environmental objectives were integrated into the first pillar for the first time¹⁶. Under the heading “environmental protection requirements”, the member states were required to take appropriate environmental measures, which included support in return for agri-environmental commitments, general mandatory environmental requirements and specific environmental requirements constituting a condition for direct payments.

The 2003 reform then enshrined the cross-compliance system, which is still in force today and ties the (full) payment of direct aid to compliance with certain rules relating to agricultural land, production and activity. Statutory management requirements (SMRs) concerning environment, public, animal and plant health, animal welfare and the maintenance of land in good agricultural and environmental condition (GAEC) were incorporated into market organisation law¹⁷.

¹⁰ G. Eckhardt, *Die Reform der CAP 2003 - Zwischenbilanz und Ausblick*, in: R. Norer, G. Holzer (eds.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2010*, Vienna/Graz 2010, p. 217.

¹¹ Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013-1308/2013, OJ 2013, L 347/487 et seq.

¹² See in detail G. Queisner, *Rahmenbedingungen für eine umweltverträgliche Landwirtschaft im Europarecht. Zugleich ein Beitrag zur Reform der CAP, Cross Compliance und Klimaschutz*, Baden-Baden 2013, p. 113 ff; G. Holzer, *Die neue "Ökoarchitektur" der CAP*, in: R. Norer, G. Holzer (eds.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2015*, Vienna/Graz 2015, pp. 122 ff. = abridged version in CEDR-JRL 1/2015, pp. 50 ff.

¹³ Regulation (EEC) No. 2078/92 on agricultural production methods compatible with the requirements of the protection of the environment and the maintenance of the countryside, OJ 1992, L 215/85.

¹⁴ Art. 22 ff. Regulation (EC) No 1257/99 on support for rural development from the European Agricultural Guidance and Guarantee Fund (EAGGF), OJ 1999, L 160/80.

¹⁵ Art. 28 Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), OJ 2013, L 347/487.

¹⁶ Cf. Art. 3 Regulation (EC) No 1259/1999 establishing common rules for direct support schemes under the common agricultural policy, OJ 1999, L 160/113.

¹⁷ Art. 3 ff. in connection with Annex III and IV Regulation (EC) No 1782/2003 establishing common rules for direct support schemes under the common agricultural policy and establishing certain support schemes for farmers, OJ 2003 L 270/1.

In addition to modifications to cross compliance¹⁸, the 2013 reform saw the additional introduction of so-called greening, whereby 30 % of the available national financial envelope is linked to the application of certain sustainable agricultural practices. In this context, part of the direct payments is made conditional on compliance with agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment¹⁹. This obligatory greening component of the basic payment thus represents a payment for ecological services rendered²⁰. The greening measures go beyond the cross-compliance requirements and include, on arable land, crop diversification and the establishment of ecological priority areas or ecologically equivalent measures as well as the maintenance of permanent grassland.

Thematically, the environmental protection issues addressed now cover an impressive range of topics based on cross-compliance requirements, greening and rural development measures: *Environmental protection in a narrow sense, nature and biodiversity conservation, water protection, animal welfare and climate protection*²¹.

Currently, the system based on agricultural competence presents itself as a complex *eco-pyramid*²², which spirals upwards in steps from mandatory to voluntary standards and from environmentally relevant sectoral legislation to cross compliance, greening and rural development. This pyramid – albeit in a modified form – will also characterise the regime of the new CAP post 2020²³.

Even if “greening the CAP” – i.e. designing the support system in accordance with the green box measures of the WTO Agreement on Agriculture (AoA)²⁴, which by definition are exempt from the dismantling obligations under international trade law – may have been at the beginning of this development, the current differentiation of the measures goes far beyond what is required under international law.

2.3 Structural and social policy

Within the framework of the common agricultural structural policy, which, in addition to market policy, was only launched later, socio-structural directives were adopted in 1972 and supplemented in 1975 by measures in favour of mountain areas and other disadvantaged areas²⁵.

¹⁸ Art. 91 ff. in connection with Annex II Regulation (EU) 1306/2013 on the financing, management and monitoring of the common agricultural policy, OJ 2013, L 347/549.

¹⁹ Art. 43 Regulation (EU) 1307/2013 establishing rules for direct payments to farmers under support schemes within the framework of the common agricultural policy, OJ 2013, L 347/608.

²⁰ J. Martínez, *Das Greening der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik*, NuR 2013, p. 692.

²¹ Detailed evidence with R. Norer, *Agrarrechtliche Weltenrettung oder Überforderung? Von der Methodik der Integration außerlandwirtschaftlicher Ansprüche ins europäische Agrarrecht*, Festschrift for Roman Budzinski, Przegład Prawa Rolnego 2/2021, pp. 353 ff.

²² G. Holzer (fn. 11), p. 133; G. Holzer, *Die neue Ökoarchitektur der GAP und ihr Beitrag zum Klimaschutz*, in: R. Norer, G. Holzer (eds.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2019*, Vienna/Graz 2019, p. 196.

²³ For the upcoming changes through CAP post 2020 see fn. 62.

²⁴ https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/14-ag_01_e.htm.

²⁵ Directive 72/159/EEC on the modernization of farms, OJ 1972, L 96/1; Directive 72/160/EEC concerning measures to encourage the cessation of farming and the reallocation of utilized agricultural area for the purposes of structural improvement, OJ 1972, L 96/9; Directive 72/161/EEC concerning the provision of socio-economic guidance for and the acquisition of occupational skills by persons engaged in agriculture, OJ 1972, L 96/15; Directive 75/268/EEC on mountain and hill farming and farming in certain less-favoured areas, OJ 1975, L 206/15.

While the accompanying measures of the MacSharry reform provided for early retirement schemes²⁶, finally in 1999 with “Agenda 2000” rural development support was created as an equal 2nd pillar of the CAP²⁷. This established the framework for Community support for sustainable development and flanked and complemented the other instruments of the Common Agricultural Policy.

Today, the 2nd CAP pillar pursues, among other things, the achievement of balanced territorial development of the rural economy and rural communities, including the creation and maintenance of jobs. One of the priorities is to promote social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas, with a focus on diversification and creation of small enterprises and jobs, fostering local development in rural areas and enhancing the accessibility of information and communication technologies in rural areas²⁸. Relevant measures are in particular the payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints²⁹.

2.4 Food safety

First of all, organic farming should be mentioned here, starting with the EC Organic Regulation in 1991. The common rules for production, labelling and control of organic (ecological) farming have been promoted in the agri-environmental programmes since 1992³⁰.

Today, food safety is part of cross compliance in Annex II of Regulation 1306/2013, consisting of two references to relevant legal standards³¹, as well as from the areas of animal identification and registration³² and animal diseases³³.

2.5 Energy policy

With the 2009 Health Check, the EAFRD Regulation was amended to allow Member States to include climate change and renewable energy projects in their development programmes³⁴.

3. Instruments

After this brief outline, the instruments used to implement this thematic expansion up to the current CAP with all its non-agricultural content will now be examined.

First of all, it should be noted that integrated policies are not only a familiar concept of European law, but are often even expressly desired. A prime example is the integration clause of Article 11 TFEU, according to which environmental protection requirements must be integrated into the definition and implementation of other Union policies and activities, in particular with a view to promoting sustainable development. According to Article 4 (2) (d) TFEU, agriculture is one of these other policies. Even

²⁶ Regulation (EEC) No 2079/92 instituting a Community aid scheme for early retirement from farming, OJ 1992, L 215/91.

²⁷ Regulation (EC) 1257/1999.

²⁸ Art. 4 lit. c and Art. 5 line 6 Regulation (EU) 1305/2013.

²⁹ Art. 31 Regulation (EU) 1305/2013.

³⁰ Cf. Art. 2 para. 1 lit. a Regulation (EEC) 2078/92 and currently Art. 29 Regulation (EU) 1305/2013.

³¹ SMR 4-5.

³² SMR 6-8.

³³ SMR 9.

³⁴ Art. 16a para. 1 lit. a and b Regulation (EC) 1698/2005, amended by Regulation (EC) No. 473/2009, OJ 2009, L 144/3.

if this requirement was expressed more pointedly in the predecessor provision of Art. 6 ECT – according to which environmental protection requirements must be “materially integrated” into the other policy areas – the pursuit of environmental policy goals by agricultural policy in particular is required today more than ever. As early as 1992, the first basis for agri-environmental measures in Art. 1 Regulation (EEC) No. 2078/92 stated that one of the intended purposes was to contribute to “the achievement of the Community’s policy objectives regarding agriculture and the environment”. The obligation to take environmental concerns into account is not limited to specific Union policies, but covers all areas of EU activity, in particular transport and energy policy in addition to agriculture³⁵.

Methodologically, three different approaches can essentially be distilled: a separation of the various legal matters (3.1.), their linkage (3.2.) and their – usually one-sided – integration (3.3.).

3.1 Separation

In terms of the law of competence and dogmatically unproblematic is the normal case of separation of the various areas of law and thus also of administrative competences. This means that European environmental law, consumer protection law, social law, energy law etc. is enacted on the basis of the relevant primary law competence (Art. 192, 169, 153, 194 TFEU), where necessary transposed into the respective specific national law and enforced by way of the common means of indirect enforcement by the national environmental, consumer protection, social and energy authorities.

3.1.1 General standards

If these are general standards, this right applies in general terms to everyone and not only to agriculture. Farmers are therefore bound by it in the same way as all other EU citizens.

As an example, the lowest level of the eco-architecture pyramid³⁶, the environmentally relevant sectoral law, can be cited here. These generally binding standards of EU and national law claim general validity and can be uniformly enforced by means of technical sanctions. However, in the case of directives, national legislators sometimes have a great deal of leeway, resulting in different environmental standards in the individual member states, which is why the tendency here is towards directly applicable regulations³⁷.

Examples include the Groundwater Directive³⁸, Water Framework Directive³⁹, Environmental Liability Directive⁴⁰ or the Natura 2000 Directives⁴¹.

³⁵ S. Heselhaus, Art. 11 TFEU, para. 21, in: M. Pechstein, C. Nowak, U. Häde (fn. 3).

³⁶ See fn. 21.

³⁷ Thus G. Holzer (fn. 11), p. 134 with examples.

³⁸ Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration, OJ 2006, L 372/19.

³⁹ Directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, OJ 2000, L 327/1.

⁴⁰ Directive 2004/35/EC on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage, OJ 2004 L 143/56.

⁴¹ Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild birds, OJ 2009, L 20/7; Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora, OJ 1992, L 206/7.

3.1.2 Specific standards

A second, somewhat different case is that in which the “other” legal matter contains agricultural-specific norms, which then – explicitly or implicitly – apply only to agriculture⁴². This means that (almost) only farmers are bound by them.

Examples of such *individual* specific standards in general regulations are the Groundwater Directive, which sets limits for nitrates and active substances in plant protection products⁴³, or the Environmental Liability Directive, which addresses agriculture as an activity⁴⁴.

Exemplary for *entire* sets of regulations of such specific standards is the Sewage Sludge Directive⁴⁵ and the Nitrates Directive⁴⁶, both of which already bear the (exclusive) reference to agriculture in their names⁴⁷.

But again, these standards have not been enacted under agricultural competence and are not (in principle) enforced by the agricultural authorities.

3.2 Linkage

A second way, which is clearly more specific to agriculture, is to link the non-agricultural areas of law with agricultural law. This gives certain norms of general specialised law a special meaning that goes beyond their general binding force. Such a link is conceivable in both directions, i.e. the “non-agricultural” norm contains a special reference to agricultural law or the link is made in the agricultural norm itself.

While no example is apparent for the first case, the second case in the environmental sector is exemplified by the already-described cross compliance⁴⁸. In this case, the statutory management requirements (SMRs) are linked to individual environmentally relevant standards of sectoral law that are in force. These must be complied with by farmers not only because of their general validity, but also because they have special effects on them under agricultural law. In the event of a violation, the sanction under sectoral law is accompanied by reductions in direct payments under the first and second pillar⁴⁹.

Here, the “non-agricultural” norm is enacted under the relevant competence norm and enforced by the respective specialised authority, but at the same time it receives a second side in that it is also enforced by the agricultural authority due to the link enacted in the agricultural competence⁵⁰.

⁴² These special norms can be exception norms (*ius singulare*) or special norms (*ius proprium*); on this see Ch. Grimm, R. Norer, *Agrarrecht*, 4th edition, Munich 2015, p. 15.

⁴³ Annex I Regulation 2006/118/EC.

⁴⁴ Art. 3 para. 1 lit. a in connection with Annex III lines 7c and 11 Directive 2004/35/EC.

⁴⁵ Directive 86/278/EEC on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture, OJ 1986, L 181/6.

⁴⁶ Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources, OJ 1991, L 375/1.

⁴⁷ Furthermore, Art. 4 and 5 Directive 91/676/EEC are the subject of the Cross Compliance Standard SMR 1; Annex II of Regulation (EU) 1306/2013.

⁴⁸ Art. 91 ff. in connection with Annex II Regulation (EU) 1306/2013.

⁴⁹ Art. 97 ff. VO (EU) 1306/2013.

⁵⁰ F.-J. Peine, *Verknüpfung der Beihilfen mit der Einhaltung von Umweltstandards – Konsequenzen*, AUR 2005 Supplement I, p. 12, speaks of a strengthening of validity.

3.3 Integration

The third possibility can be seen in the fact that agricultural law regulates the extraneous matter itself. In this case, it is a matter of genuine agricultural law norms, which are enacted under agricultural competence and enforced exclusively by the agricultural administration.

Greening is an example of this. Here, agricultural law formulates land management methods that promote climate and environmental protection, compliance with which must already be demonstrated in the multiple claim. In the event of violations, a complicated graduated system of reductions in the eco-premium is applied⁵¹. Another example is the wide range of rural development measures based on European and national agricultural law, which are entered into voluntarily and whose standard must exceed that of cross compliance and greening.

4. Analysis

4.1 Assessment

The *separation* proves to be the legal normal case. Like all other general norms, the relevant legal material is enforced by the respective competent (non-agricultural) authority and any infringements either affect farmers like all other citizens (general norm) or (almost) exclusively farmers (specific norm).

In terms of *linkage*, cross compliance has been able to maintain a fixed position that has outlasted all reform stages since then, despite numerous critical legal questions associated with it^{52,53}. On the contrary, the literature even calls for a readjustment with regard to a stronger unification of the standards^{54,55}.

From the series of legal questions, only the problem of competence should be addressed here. Accordingly, cross compliance leads to the fact that essential parts of environmental law are ultimately enforced by agricultural law and, due to the efficient funding controls, generally gain significantly in steering effect⁵⁶. In this process, the norms of environmental law mutate, as it were, into agricultural law norms by virtue of linking for the purposes of the Horizontal CAP Regulation, which according to jurisprudential dogma⁵⁷ can be described as so-called subsidiary agricultural law. The relevant norms remain in the non-agricultural matter, but by virtue of reference in agricultural-specific contexts they acquire a second legal nature, as it were. If they have thus become a norm of agricultural law in this

⁵¹ Art. 24-29 Delegated Regulation (EU) 640/2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) 1306/2013, OJ 2014, L 181/48.

⁵² R. Norer, *Rechtsfragen der EU-Agrarreform*, Vienna/Graz 2007, pp. 107 ff.; for a synopsis of the fundamental legal questions raised in the literature see G. Holzer (fn. 11), pp. 140 ff.

⁵³ G. Eckhardt (fn. 9), p. 103, even speaks of a quantum leap.

⁵⁴ This uniformity currently depends mainly on the implementation practice of the individual Member States, as the SMR linkage is mostly based on EU directives, which inevitably leads to inconsistent standards due to the different implementation in the individual Member States. However, this is also and even more evident in the integration of the requirements for GAEC, where various minimum requirements are specified for certain topics to be filled in by the Member States at national or regional level. For details on the regulatory technique and content, see G. Holzer (fn. 11), pp. 136 ff.

⁵⁵ G. Holzer (fn. 11), p. 143.

⁵⁶ R. Norer (fn. 51), p. 125 f.; G. Holzer, (fn. 11), p. 141.

⁵⁷ For example, in the relationship between administrative law and civil law, P. Tschannen, U. Zimmerli, M. Müller, *Allgemeines Verwaltungsrecht*, 4th edition, Bern 2014, p. 130.

context, it is also justified that they are enforced and sanctioned by the agricultural authorities. This is at the expense of the agricultural budget⁵⁸.

Finally, in the case of *integration*, “non-agricultural” content from the specialised law is not brought into agricultural law, as it were, as in the case of linking, but is formulated in agricultural law itself.

In this context, the question may arise as to whether such norms may be legally enacted by the agricultural legislator at all. However, the ECJ has repeatedly confirmed in numerous rulings that the agricultural competence of (currently) Art. 43 TFEU is to be interpreted broadly. In the case of BSE measures and agri-environmental measures, for example, the Court of Justice has found that, in contrast to the article on consumer protection and environmental competence, agricultural competence is sufficient, since a legal act that has two objectives must be based on the essential or predominant component.⁵⁹

Whether the implementation of environmental measures in Pillar 1 enables the efficient achievement of environmental goals at all is judged differently with reference to the blanket application⁶⁰.

4.2 Comparison

In an overall view of all three methods described here, both separation and integration prove to be largely unproblematic from a legal point of view. In the case of separation, the non-agricultural authorities enforce their own matters for all those affected by them (farmers or not); in the case of integration, the agricultural authorities enforce their own agricultural law. In this respect, non-agricultural inclusions are also agricultural law, which is enacted by the agricultural legislators after a political compromise. This means that it is hardly ever “unadulterated” environmental, social or food law, but rather a version tailored to agriculture, which in this respect should be highly suitable for achieving the goals pursued with it.

Only in the case of linkage do legal problems become apparent, although this method has shown itself to be surprisingly resistant since its introduction and still does. Conceptually, it is not surprising that legal friction arises when a norm designed for another area of law is applied *tel quel* in agricultural law. The underlying idea sees the granting of agricultural subsidies as going beyond agricultural law from an overall societal perspective. For example, a livestock farmer who uses banned antibiotics would have to face criminal proceedings including a fine “outside of agricultural law”, but could keep the direct payments granted by the Union without a link. This could not be made comprehensible to the public and could not be reconciled with the state’s function as a role model⁶¹. In this respect, compliance with the standards would also be in the interest of the CAP itself, as this would increase the social acceptance of agricultural subsidies⁶².

⁵⁸ R. Norer (fn. 51), p. 126, according to which a distinction must be made between the legal and the legal-political side.

⁵⁹ ECJ, Case C-269/97, [2000] ECR I-2257; Case C-336/00, [2002] ECR I-7699. On conflict of laws, see R. Norer, Art. 43 TFEU, para. 5, in: M. Pechstein, C. Nowak, U. Häde (fn. 3).

⁶⁰ Thus B. Mittermüller, *Die Ökoprämie und ihre „eigentümliche“ Rechtsnatur*, in: R. Norer, G. Holzer (eds.), *Agarrrecht Jahrbuch 2014*, Vienna/Graz 2014, p. 161; B. Heinrich, C. Holst, S. Lakner, *Die Reform der gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik: Wird alles grüner und gerechter?*, GAIA 22/1, 2013, pp. 22 f.; contrary G. Holzer (fn. 11), p. 151.

⁶¹ R. Norer (fn. 51), pp. 104 f. with further references.

⁶² Ch. Busse, Art. 40 TFEU para. 79, in: C. O. Lenz, K.-D. Borchardt (eds.), *EU- Verträge Kommentar*, 6th edition, Cologne/Vienna 2012.

4.3 Result

From a regulatory perspective, then, three instruments are available. In the eco-pyramid described above, all three regulatory techniques are currently condensed. At the bottom is the separation in the case of environmentally relevant sectoral law (= general environmental law), then the linking in the case of cross-compliance and at the top the integration in the case of greening and agri-environmental measures⁶³. These instruments can only be successful if certain conditions are met in each case.

The separation presupposes not only that non-agricultural law can be effectively enforced by non-agricultural authorities, but also an agricultural law cleansed of non-agricultural claims. This would ultimately mean that (once again) each policy would legislate and enforce for itself: environmental policy would be environmental policy, structural policy would be structural policy, climate policy would be climate policy, etc. with clearly delineated competences and budgets⁶⁴. This would, however, significantly reduce the scope and (also financial) importance of agricultural law, and set it back to its historical core tasks within the meaning of Art. 39 TFEU, in particular the fulfilment of the food function.

Integration presupposes not only the incorporation of non-agricultural claims into agricultural law, but ultimately also the exemption of agriculture from the application of general law. This would mean a multifaceted agricultural policy that wants to meet all non-agricultural demands and that would set out to save the world as a superhero: the environment the day before yesterday, food safety yesterday, animal welfare today, the climate tomorrow and whatever the day after tomorrow. This would inevitably overtax agricultural law, which would run the risk of becoming without contours and arbitrary.

Seen in this light, the least convincing instrument from a purely legal point of view, namely linkage, is perhaps the most feasible between segregation under agricultural law and excessive demands. A world rescue in miniature with methodological flaws, so to speak.

⁶³ The most recent CAP reform stage will bring about changes in the subject area dealt with here insofar as the current three-tier eco-architecture (cross compliance, greening, agri-environmental and climate measures) will be reduced to two tiers. To this end, greening will be merged into the cross-compliance system under the new title of eco-conditionality. This will again significantly increase the “baseline” and change the normative ground of validity. In addition, the climate and environment-related payments envisaged in both pillars will go beyond; R. Mögele, I.E. Rusu, *The Commission's proposals for the Common Agricultural Policy after 2020*, CEDR-JRL 2/2018, p. 12; in detail G. Holzer (fn. 21), pp. 196 ff. and most recently G. Holzer, *Ökoarchitektur der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik im Umbruch*, in: J. Martínez (ed.), *Jahrbuch des Agrarrechts* Vol. XV, Baden-Baden 2021, pp. 71 ff.

⁶⁴ In this direction already R. Norer, *Synthesis Report*, in: C.E.D.R. (ed.), *CAP Reform: Market Organisation and Rural Areas. Legal Framework and Implementation*. XXVIII European Congress and Colloquium of Agricultural Law, Potsdam. 9-13 September 2015, Baden-Baden 2017, p. 423.